

“A Comparative Study To Assess The Knowledge And Attitude Of Mothers Of Under 5 Year Children Regarding The Importance Of Outdoor Play Needs In Rural And Urban Area Of Jabalpur (M.P.)”

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ABSTRACT: Outdoor play is essential for the physical, emotional, and cognitive development of children under 5 years. However, there is a growing concern that children are spending less time outdoors, leading to a range of negative consequences.

Background of study: Outdoor play is essential for the physical, emotional, and cognitive development of children under 5 years. However, there is a growing concern that children are spending less time outdoors, leading to a range of negative consequences.

The knowledge and attitude of mothers of under 5 year children regarding the importance of outdoor play needs in rural and urban area of Jabalpur. A descriptive comparative study was conducted among 60 mothers of children under 5 years, divided into two groups: urban and rural. A structured questionnaire and Likert scale was used to assess the knowledge and attitude of mothers. The study revealed significant differences in the knowledge and attitude of urban and rural mothers regarding outdoor play. Urban mothers had better knowledge, but a more negative attitude towards outdoor play, safety concerns and lack of access to outdoor spaces. The major finding indicates that rural mean 5.33 and SD 2.03 and urban mean 6.73 and SD 1.6and their co- relation is 1.05 .The major finding Indicates that the rural mean 43.96 and SD 10.23 and urban mean 88.58 and SD 10.002 and their co- relation is 0.00065.

Keywords: Mothers ,under 5 year children , outdoor play needs

INTRODUCTION

“let the children be free encourage them run outside when it is raining, let them remove their shoes when they find a puddle of water and when the grass of the meadows is wet with dew, let them rest peacefully when a tree invites them to sleep beneath.”

Play is a universal language of children. It is one of the most important forms of communication and can be an effective technique in relating to them. Parents are child's first and best play mates. The most creative children are those who have had parents involved in their play. This study was conducted to assess and compare the knowledge of mothers of under-five children regarding importance of play in growth and development. There is a growing body of research that shows a link between play and the development of cognitive and social skills that are prerequisites for learning more complex concepts as children get older. For example, play is linked to growth in memory, self-regulation, oral language, and recognizing symbols. It has been linked to higher levels of school adjustment and increased social development. Play has also been linked to increased literacy skills and other areas of academic learning (a view held by Piagetian and Vygotskian theories of child development). Play is especially beneficial to children's learning when it reaches a certain. degree of sophistication. In other words, “unproductive” play happens not only when children fight and argue over who is going to be the “mommy” and who is going to be the “baby,” but also when the child who is “mommy” keeps performing the same

routines with her "baby" day after day with no change. By contrast, play that has a potential for fostering many areas of young children's development, including social and cognitive development, has the following characteristics:

- 1) Children create a pretend scenario by negotiating and talking to peers and use props in a symbolic way.
- 2) Children create specific roles-and rules-for pretend behaviour and adopt multiple themes and multiple roles.

When children engage in this kind of play for most of their early years, they learn to delay gratification and to prioritize their goals and actions. They also learn to consider the perspectives and needs of other people. They learn to represent things symbolically and to regulate their behaviours and act in a deliberate, intentional way.

OBJECTIVES

1. Assess the knowledge of mothers of under 5 year children regarding the importance of outdoor play needs.
2. Assess the attitude of mothers of under 5 year children regarding the importance of outdoor play needs.
3. To compare the knowledge of mothers of under 5 year children regarding the importance of outdoor play needs rural & urban.
4. To compare the attitude of mothers of under 5 year children regarding the importance of outdoor play needs rural & urban.
5. Determine the association between knowledge score of mothers of under 5 year children of urban area with their selected demographic variables.
6. Determine the association between attitude score of mothers of under 5 year children of urban area with their selected demographic variables.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of literature is a summary of all the reviews from various research literature related to the current study carried out by the researcher. It helps to discover what is already known about the research problem and what more has to be done.

Ali Hasan ,Madhu Gupta 2024 (March /April) A STP study was conducted on Lucknow to assess the effectiveness of structure teaching program on knowledge regarding impact of outdoor play on child growth and development 17 among the primary care giver of under 5 year children at selected School of Lucknow . A quantitative evaluative research approach was adopted for the study non probability convenient sampling techniques some consist 50 mothers of under 5 year children .The study revealed that STP by comparing pre test and post test knowledge level in primary care giver of under 5 children . According to pre-test knowledge among 50 care giver of under 5 year children 74% have inadequate knowledge 13% have moderate adequate knowledge 0% were having adequate knowledge. According to the post level of knowledge 0% were have inadequate knowledge, 44% were have moderate adequate knowledge ,and 56% were having adequate knowledge regarding the impact of outdoor play on child growth and development .The mean of pre-test knowledge 13.78 and the mean value of post test knowledge is 24.54 and the difference comes 10.76 .

Jeena jose, Anu V kumar (2023) There is non experimental descriptive study was conducted on asses the knowledge regarding play need among mother of under 5 year children in a selected Hospital Ernakulam district, Kerala 60 mother consist of this study non probability convenient sampling technique used in this study. it was found that 11% of mother have very poor knowledge and remaining 17% of mother have two or knowledge(62%) of mother have average knowledge and the remaining 10% of mother have good knowledge.

Methodology:

A descriptive comparative study was conducted among 60 mothers of under 5 years children, divided into two groups: urban and rural. A structured questionnaire and likert scale was used to assess the knowledge and attitude of mothers.

Tool of instruments-

Tool used for study is structured questionnaire and likert scale. The tool consist of three section A ,B & C

Section A - This show socio demographic variables.

Section B - Likert scale related to attitude of mothers regarding the importance of outdoor play needs.

Section C - Questionnaire related to knowledge of mothers regarding the importance of outdoor play needs.

Section A- There are 8 socio- demographic variables Age of mother, education, occupation, monthly income, Type of family, No. of children, Age of child, Residence (rural/urban)

Section B- This consists of 20 questions likert scale to assess the attitude of mothers regarding the importance of outdoor play needs.

Section C- This consists of 10 structured questionnaires to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding the importance of outdoor play needs.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. Maximum 24 (40%) in the age group of 21-25 year, 24 (40%) are in the age group 25-28 year 6 (10%) are in the age group 29-32 year, and 6 (10%) are in the age group of 32-35 year.
2. Maximum 1(2%) are uneducated , 24 (40%) are primary or middle education , 24 (40%) are high school education 11 (18%)are graduate and post graduated in level of education
3. Maximum 4 (7%) are in government job 38 (63%)are housewife 9 (15 %) are business women 9 (50%)are private job
4. Maximum 15 (25%) having monthly income less than 5000 35 (58.30%) having 5000 to 50000 to 14% having 15000 se 25000 and 2(4%) having 25000 or above
5. Maximum 24 (40%) are nuclear family 35 (58.30%) are joint family 1 (2%)are single parent and 0(0%) are in extended family.
6. Maximum 30 (50%) are rural residence and 30 (50%) are urban Residence .
7. Maximum 12 (20%) have are children in family 38 (63.30%) have two children 10 (17%) have three children 0 (0%)have 4 and above children in family.
8. Maximum 12 (20%) have under 2 year 21 (35%)have under 3 year 19 (32%) have under 4 year and 8 (13.30%) have under 5 year.

ASSESSMENT OF RURAL MOTHER UNDER 5 YEAR CHILDREN KNOWLEDGE REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF OUTDOOR PLAY NEEDS

The table fulfill the objective 3 clearly indicates that 14 mothers have poor knowledge, 15 mother have average knowledge,

S. N O.	CATEG ORIES	FREQE NCY	PERCEN TAGE	MEA N	SD
1	Poor	14	46.6%	5.53	2.03
2	Average	15	50%		
3	Good	1	3.3%		

and 1mother have good knowledge regarding the importance of outdoor play needs. The mean 5.53 and SD2.03

Finding related to assess the knowledge score of rural mothers under 5 year children .The table fulfill the objective 3 clearly indicates that 14 mothers have poor knowledge,

15 mother have average knowledge and 1 mother have good knowledge regarding the importance of outdoor play needs. The mean 5.53 and SD2.03

S.N O.	CATEGORI ES	FREQEN CY	PERCEN TAGE	ME AN	S D
1	Poor	7	23.3%	6.73	1.6
2	Average	20	66.6%		
3	Good	3	10%		

CORRELATION BETWEEN RURAL & URBAN MOTHER UNDER 5 YEAR CHILDREN KNOWLEDGE REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF OUTDOOR PLAY NEEDS.

S.NO.	DISCRIPTION	MEAN	SD	CR
1	RURAL	5.53	2.03	1.05
2	URBAN	6.73	1.6	

The table no. 13 the objectives clearly indicates that rural means 5.33 and SD 2.03and urban mean 6.73 and SD 1.6and their co- relation is 1.05

The table the objectives clearly indicates that 5 mother have unfavorable attitude 25 mother have moderately

attitude , and 0 mother have attitude regarding the importance of outdoor play needs the mean.

S.N O.	CATEG ORIES	FREQE NCY	PERCEN TAGE	ME AN	S D
1	Unfavora ble	5	16.6%	43.96	10.23
2	Moderat ely	25	83.3%		
3	Favorabl e	0	0%		

ASSESSMENT OF URBAN MOTHER UNDER 5 YEAR CHILDREN ATTITUDE REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF OUTDOOR PLAY NEEDS.

S.NO.	CATEGORIES	FREQENCY	PERCENTAGE	MEAN	SD
1	Unfavorable	4	13.3%	88.58	10.002
2	Moderately	26	76.6%		
3	Favorable	3	10%		

The table no.12 the objectives clearly indicates that 4 mother have unfavorable attitude 26 mother have moderately attitude , and 3 mother have favorable attitude regarding the importance of outdoor play needs the means.

S.NO.	DISCRIPTION	MEAN	SD	CR
1	RURAL	43.96	10.23	0.00065
2	URBAN	88.58	10.002	

CORRELATION BETWEEN RURAL & URBAN MOTHER UNDER 5 YEAR CHILDREN ATTITUDE REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF OUTDOOR PLAY NEEDS.

NURSING IMPLICATIONS

NURSING ADMINISTRATION

Finding of the study can be used by the nursing administrate in creating policies and plans for providing education to the students. This will contributable the students to increase knowledge regarding benefits of outdoor play recognition of changes in health and request for appropriate interventions.

NURSING RESEARCH

Research should be continued on newer practices and methods of teaching focusing on effective child physical, social, language, cognitive and emotional development by play and importance of play in different age groups.

CONCLUSION

This comparative study aimed to assess the knowledge and attitude of mothers regarding the importance of outdoor play needs for children under 5 years. The findings revealed significant differences in knowledge and attitude between mothers from urban and rural areas. Mothers from urban areas demonstrated better knowledge about the importance of outdoor play for their children's physical, emotional, and cognitive development. However, their attitude towards outdoor play was influenced by concerns about safety, pollution, and lack of access to outdoor play spaces. In contrast, mothers from rural areas had limited knowledge about the benefits of outdoor play, but their attitude was more positive, with many recognizing the importance of outdoor play for their children's overall well-being. The study highlights the need for targeted interventions to educate mothers about the importance of outdoor play, particularly in rural areas. Additionally, urban planners and policymakers should prioritize the creation of safe and accessible outdoor play spaces for young children.

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